

Immunohistochemical localization of constitutive and inducible Heat Shock Protein 70 in carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) exposed to transport stress

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Abstract

In the present work we investigated by immunohistochemistry the cellular localization of constitutive as well as inducible heat shock protein 70 in several tissues of common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) exposed to transport stress. In carp, the constitutive form (HSC70) was detected only in red skeletal muscle of both control and stressed animals. In the same species, the inducible form (HSP70) was evident in the epithelia of renal tubules, gills and skin of stressed animals, whereas in controls only red skeletal muscle exhibited an immunopositivity to HSP70 antibody. In trout, immunostaining to HSC70 antibody was found mainly in the epithelia of intestine, gills and skin of both control and stressed animals although the reactivity was generally higher in animals exposed to transport stress. In the same species immunostaining to HSP70 antibody was observed only in red skeletal muscle and epidermis of control animals.